

EFFECT OF SHATDHAUTH GHRITA MODIFIED WITH HARIDRA, NEEM, YASHTIMADHU AND KOKUM BUTTER ON PADADARI (CRACKED HEELS): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Have you looked at your feet recently and thought your heels have had better days? Cracked foot is a common cosmetic and most neglected problem for both men and women in India. Cracked heels, known as heel fissures, are a prevalent dermatological condition characterized by dry and thickened skin that may progress to result in painful cracks. In persons who are in the habit of too much walking on rough ground without footwear, this habits increased the *Rukhata*, *Kharata* which leads to increased in the *vata dosha*, producing fissures in the sole of feet. When the cracks are deep, they become painful and even bleed on minor pressure exerted on them. In certain cases, they get infected and cause severe pain and discomfort hindering the daily activity of the patient. Here, in this article we discuss the case report of *Padadari* in *Ayurveda*, how we treated with using some Ayurveda drugs, local as well as systemic treatment and how the patient responded to the treatment.

KEYWORDS: PADADARI, SHATDHAUTHGHRITA, CRACKED FEET.

INTRODUCTION

Cracked foot is a common cosmetic problem for both men and women in India, with some studies showing a prevalence of over 40% in the general adult population and higher rates in specific demographics, such as females and certain occupational groups like farmers and housewives. One study in rural area of south district were found a 48% overall prevalence in adults with significantly higher rates in women (58.4%) compared to men (33.3%).^[1]

Most women get their teeth cleaned at least once a year, keep tabs on their heart, and may even have an annual eye checkup. While they might clip and paint their nails on a regular basis, but women often neglect the health of their feet. Cracked heels, known as heel fissures, are a prevalent dermatological condition characterized by dry and thickened skin that may progress to result in painful cracks. In *Ayurveda*, the cracked heel is correlated with *Padadari*, which comes under the heading of *Kshudra rogas*. It occurs due to excessive walking, walking on uneven surfaces, and excessively practicing foods and regimens, which increase *Vata*.

As per *Ayurvedic Science*, symptoms of cracked foot can be correlated to that of *Padadari* (Cracked foot). The word “*Pada*” means heel & feet, and “*Dari*” means cracks. *Padadari* is described in *Ayurveda* under *Kshudra roga* by *Sushruta*, *Madhava Nidana*, *Bhavaprakasha* and *Yogaratanakara*. According to *Sushruta Samhita*, the predominant clinical features of *Padadari* (Cracked foot) are *Padayo dari* (Cracks on foot), *Saruja* (Associated with pain) and *Rukshata* (Roughness and dryness).^[2]

Acharya Susruta has explained for the management of *Padadari* includes *Siravedha* (puncture of the veins of the feet) and treatment of the affected part with *swedana*. *Ayurveda* also recommends used of ointment or paste to the affected part with composed of *Madhucchishta* i.e Bees wax, *Vasa* (lard), *Majja* (marrow), powder of *Sarja Rasa* (resin obtained from *Shorea robusta Gaertn.*), clarified butter, *Yavakshara* (alkaline formulation prepared from ash of *Hordeum vulgare L.*) and *Gairika* (Red ochre) etc. by using above treatment protocol *Shatdhuatghrita* is modified with adding *Haridra*, *Nimb*, *yastimadhu* and *Kokum* butter as per the condition for this case study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Case report- Patient Information

A 32-year-female patient, non-diabetic, non-hypertensive with k/c/o hypothyroidism visited Outpatient Department of Panchakarma, complaining of the appearance of cracks in both feet associated with pain for the past three month. After detailed history-taking revealed that the patient is working in railways department. The patient started experiencing dryness in feet from 2 months but ignored the signs. A week later, cracks began appearing on the soles of the heel, accompanied with pain and blackish discoloration. Within twenty days, the cracks started lengthening and deepening. The patient also noticed increasing pain while performing routine activities. Due to working in the workshop patients has to walk in the workshop daily, so around working duration of eight hours roughly five hours she needs to stand for long time and walking on hard surface daily. While taking history patients told about taking the protein shake before going to plan for the second child, for weight reduction of one of the famous product of known reputed company. And always skip the meal.

Personal history

Bowel habit was Regular, Appetite – not good , Marital History –married, having two children one male child is of 5 years age and other girl child is of 9 month age, Occupation – working, Menstrual history – regular, Addiction – No, Family History-None. All other vital and systemic examination were within normal limits. Weight– 68kg.

Local Examination

Site of lesion - sole of both the foot with Symmetrical (both soles) Distribution including phalanges, Dryness, cracking of both the soles is seen with facing bleed intermittently from the cracked region. Surface is rough and dry, margins are – irregular with itching and sever pain while standing and walking.

Diagnosis

The diagnosis was based on the clinical presentation of the condition. *Paddari* was taken as a differential diagnosis. It is classified under Kshudra Kushta caused due to vitiation of Vata and Kapha Dosha and is chiefly characterized by *Pani Pada Sphutana* (Cracks on Palms and Soles) accompanied with *Teevra Vedana* (Severe Pain).^[3]

Cracked foot are splits or cracks in the epidermis, which can manifest as a consequence of an fibrosis and may or may not present with hyperkeratosis. Epidermal

fissures are superficial and not considered to be a wound at this early stage. However, with increased pressure these splits become deeper, involving the dermis so that they begin to bleed and result in pain on weight-bearing activities. These fissures are regarded as partial-thickness skin wounds and are at increased risk of developing infection. Full-thickness ulcer formation can occur if the fissure progresses further, resulting in an open wound that has the potential to lead to deeper infection and cellulites, especially in patients with diabetes and peripheral vascular disease.^[4]

In general anyone can get a cracked heel or fissure soles but certain conditions are predisposing to fissure soles such as Congenital causes like Juvenile Plantar Dermatitis, Acquired causes -Eczema, Atopic Dermatitis, Tinea pedis, Psoriasis especially Palmoplantar psoriasis, Palmoplantar Keratodermas, Leprosy, Systemic causes-Diabetes mellitus, Hypothyroidism, Scleroderma, Rheumatoid arthritis.

Therapeutic intervention

The patient was advised for local application of *Shatdhaut ghrita* (modified with addition of *Haridra*, *Nimb*, *yastimadhu* and Kokum butter) twice in a day for a period of one month. Than follow-up after the seven days of the treatment begins. The patient was instructed to apply the paste after cleaning the feet with *ubatan* powder (a herbal powder prepared with mixing some ayurveda herbs like *triphala*, *manjishtha*, *sariva musta*) etc. And soaking feet in lukewarm water for 10 minutes. Later, the paste was applied to the soaked wet heels after removing the excess water. During treatment, the patient was instructed to avoid using moisturizers, harsh soaps, and thin-soled footwear's. Along with the local application treatment some oral medication were also provide for the expulsion of *dosha*.

Treatment and line of Management

After evaluation properly patient were treated with local and systemic treatment.

Start with *Deepan* and *Pachan* treatment than focused on *Ras pachak* --- *anuloman/Sratsan* and local treatment.

1st day of treatment start (for next 7 days).

Sr. no.	Name of Medicine	Dose	Frequency	Mode of administration
1	<i>Shankhvati</i>	125 mg.	2 tabs. Two times with Luke warm water before food. For 7 days.	Orally

2	<i>Erandbhrushtha Haritaki</i>	250 mg.	2 tabs. At bed time with Luke warm water for 7 days.	Orally
3	<i>Ubatan Powder for cleaning (balanceveda ubatan powder)</i>	15 gm.	Daily two times	For rubbing/ cleaning the foot and sole
4	<i>Shatdhauth ghrita</i> (added with <i>Haridra, Nimb, yastimadhu</i> and Kokum butter)	5 gm.	Two time in a day	For external application /gentle massage on foot

1st follow up after 7 days

Sr. no.	Name of Medicine	Dose	Frequency	Mode of administration
1	<i>Panchatiktaghrita goggulu</i>	500 mg	2 tab. 2 times in a day with Luke warm water for 15 days.	
2	<i>Avipattikar churna</i>	6 mg.	At bed time with Luke warm water for 15 days.	Orally
3	<i>Ubatan Powder for cleaning (balanceveda ubatan powder)</i>	15 gm.	Daily two times	For rubbing/ cleaning the foot and sole
4	<i>Shatdhauth ghrita</i> (added with <i>Haridra, Nimb, yastimadhu</i> and Kokum butter)	5 gm.	Two time in a day	For external application /gentle massage on foot

2nd follow up (after 22nd days of treatment start)

Sr.no.	Name of Medicine	Dose	Frequency	Mode of administration
1	<i>Panchatiktaghrita goggulu</i>	500 mg	2 tab. 2 times in a day with Luke warm water for 7 days.	
2	<i>Avipattikar churna</i>	6 mg.	At bed time with Luke warm water for 7 days.	Orally
3	<i>Ubatan Powder for cleaning (balanceveda ubatan powder)</i>	15 gm.	Daily two times	For rubbing/ cleaning the foot and sole
4	<i>Shatdhauth ghrita</i> (added with <i>Haridra, Nimb, yastimadhu</i> and Kokum butter)	5 gm.	Two time in a day	For external application /gentle massage on foot

3rd follow up on 30th days after treatment start

Sr. no.	Name of Medicine	Dose	Frequency	Mode of administration
1	<i>Panchatiktaghrita goggulu</i>	500 mg	2 tab. 2 times in a day with Luke warm water	

			for 7 days.	
2	<i>Avipattikar churna</i>	6 mg.	At bed time with luke warm water for 7 days.	Orally
3	<i>Ubatan Powder for cleaning (balanceveda ubatan powder)</i>	15 gm.	Daily two times	For rubbing/ cleaning the foot and sole
4	<i>Shatdhauth ghrita</i> (added with <i>Haridra, Nimb, yastimadhu</i> and Kokum butter)	5 gm.	Two time in a day	For external application /gentle massage on foot

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

The condition was assessed every seven days up to four weeks and the pictures of the foot were taken on each visit. A considerable decrease in pain was found in the first seven days after applying the medicine paste. A decrease in roughness and dryness around the heels was found after two weeks. Moderate healing of cracks was found on the second follow-up. Significant improvement in all signs and symptoms was seen in the third follow-up. The condition is much better and almost all improved on fourth follow-up. As shown in figure below.

Figure_1- Before treatment

Figure_2-After treatment

Before treatment, severe cracks, intermittent bleeding, pain, dryness was observe. During treatment, gradual improvement in conditions of cracks and pain were noted. By the end of third follow-up, approximately complete resolution of cracks, pain alleviation, and cessation of dryness and bleeding were observed, confirming the Ayurveda's effectiveness in managing *Padadari*.

DISCUSSION

The drug selected for the study *Shatdhaut ghrita* (modified with addition of *Haridra*, *Nimb*, *yastimadhu* and Kokum butter) were helpful for the management of conditions as some pitta involvement is also there so need to provide internal medicine for the *dosha shodhan* purpose.

In the *shatdhaut ghrut* mainly *ghrita* (clarified butter) used prepared from mixing water (100 times washed ghee), It contains approximately 8% lower saturated fatty acids, making it easily for absorption. These are the most edible fats and are not found in any other edible oil or fat. It contains vitamins, including Vit A and Vit. E is anti -oxidants and is helpful in reducing ketone bodies, helpful in preventing oxidative injury to the body. This process of washing 100 times with water turns ghee into a soft, cooling, nourishing, silky ointment that can be used as a traditional moisturizer and anti-wrinkle skin cream. It is excellent for damaged skin because ghee penetrates and nourishes all seven layers of tissue. In many different skin conditions, including burns, wound scars, skin marks, burning sensation, herpes, etc.^[5]

The turmeric used is exfoliates and repairs damaged skin, promotes the skin's regeneration, diminishes the appearance of the signs of ageing, and soothes and facilitates the healing of abrasions. It prevents harmful bacteria from entering the body through chapped and broken skin by providing the skin with a layer of protection against external irritants with its properties of anti ageing, anti bacterial diminish dark spots and even skin tone, promoting a healthy, glowing complexion etc. Its antibacterial properties help eliminate the bacteria that cause breakouts, while its anti-inflammatory effects reduce the associated redness, swelling, and irritation. It also helps control excess sebum (oil) production, which can lead to clogged pores.

The active compounds in *Neem*, such as nimbidin, possess strong anti-inflammatory properties that can soothe red, irritated, or sensitive skin, as a natural exfoliator, *neem* powder helps to draw out impurities and excess oil from the pores. It removes dead skin cells and dirt.^[6]

Kokum butter functions on the skin by providing deep moisturization, improving the skin's natural barrier to retain moisture, soothing irritation and inflammation, and promoting cell regeneration to aid in healing damaged or cracked skin.^[7]

Yahstimadhu offers numerous skin benefits due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and skin-regeneration properties. It helps protect against UV damage, reduces redness and inflammation conditions and aids in treating acne and hyperpigmentation, leading to improved complexion and a brighter, healthier glow.^[8]

Rubbing with *ubatan* powder will reduced the dead skin from the foot area deep clean the pores help for the regeneration, Soaking feet in lukewarm water prior to the application of paste helps in Pacifying *Vata dosha*, increases the blood flow to that area and increases the absorption of the medicine through the skin.

CONCLUSION

Cracked heel is a common condition which affects every individual at least once during their lifetime. Most of the females were affected as they did not take care due to busy schedule in management of family, also the foot care is not commonly seen during day today life, and it is most neglected part. But *Ayurveda* is only the branch which focused on foot care as daily regimen of *Paddabhyang* (massage of feet daily) on its daily regimen to stay healthy and happy. The present case reveals that following the Ayurvedic line of treatment is very effective tool for the management of any disease like Crack Heel. The present case proves *Shatdhaut ghruta* (modified with addition of *Haridra*, *Nimb*, *yastimadhu* and Kokum butter) is a potent herbomineral medicine for the treatment of *Padadari* (Cracked heels).

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